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Research Article

A PROSPECTIVE STUDY ON PRESCRIBING PATTERN OF ANTIBIOTICS ACCORDING TO WHO PRESCRIBING INDICATORS IN GENERAL MEDICINE DEPARTMENT IN TERTIARY CARE TEACHING HOSPITAL

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Abstract:

***Aim:** of the study is to monitor and assess the prescribing patterns of antibiotics in a tertiary care teaching hospital by using WHO prescribing indicators in RIMS Hospital, Kadapa.*

***Objectives:** To assess the prescribing patterns of antibiotic in General medicine population by using WHO prescribing indicators. To know the common diseases and common class of antibiotic prescribed and their indication for Therapy and to evaluate number of single or Combination of antibiotic in the prescription.*

Methods and Materials:

This is a prospective study observational study done from august to January from general medicine department of RIMS, kadapa. The data will be collected from Inpatients department in RIMS government hospital, Kadapa. Demographics characteristics of the patient from the case sheets. Data would be collected from case notes and personnel interview of the subjects who are included in the study at General medicine I.P department. Microsoft excel is used for recording and analysing the data of recruited subjects, and the results were applied in percentage.

***Results:** A total on of 300 patients included in our study, the percentage of male and female were 54.0% and 46.0% respectively. Data was collected using patient case sheets, and direct patient interviews. Information on antibiotic prescription in the study Cephalosporin antibiotics 192 (33.9%) were most frequently prescribed antibiotics followed by Penicillin's 125(22.1%).101(17.8%) were of Macrolide's 56(9.9%) were of Tetracycline's 50(8.89%) were of Fluroquinolones. In this study we observe that most of the drugs prescribed in the form of injections (64%) followed by tablets (38%) and capsule (2.1) % of the total 300 prescriptions, 124 (42%) prescription with antibiotic dual therapy,112 (37%) prescription with antibiotic monotherapy,64(21%) prescription with three or more than three antibiotic agents were observed.*

Conclusion:

In our study we observed COPD disease most common disease. Cephalosporins were most commonly prescribed class of antibiotics. Among them ceftriaxone was most prescribed antibiotics. Generic prescribing was comparatively higher and mainly prescribed from Essential Drug List. The parenteral use of antibiotics administration was markedly higher. Strict adherence to the prescription policy can significantly overcome the overuse of antibiotics and reduce the development of resistance to antibiotics.

***Keywords:** Antibiotics, Inpatients, prescribing pattern, WHO drug use indicators.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Antibiotics are molecules that kill, or stop the growth of, microorganism, including both bacteria and fungi. Antibiotics have effectively prolonged the life expectancy. Antibiotics are currently the most commonly prescribed drugs in hospitals, worldwide. But, excessive and inappropriate use of antibiotics renders increased drug resistance. The first antibiotics were prescribed in the late 1930s, beginning a great year in discovery, development and prescription. Different antibiotics have different modes of action. The study of prescribing pattern infers to monitor, evaluate, and suggest modifications in the practitioner's prescription habits, so as to make patient care reasonable and effective. The knowledge about antibiotic utilization patterns is necessary for a constructive approach to problems that arise from multiple antibiotic usages. It is extremely important that institutions and hospitals should have an antibiotic policy and ensure that the best choices are made by individual prescribers. A highly representative data aid the prescribers in rational antibiotic use and can improve the quality of patient care.

Prescription pattern monitoring studies (PPMS) are a tool for assessing the prescribing, dispensing and distribution of medicines. Prescription pattern monitoring studies (PPMS) are drug utilization studies with the main focus on prescribing, dispensing and administering of drugs. They promote appropriate use of monitored drugs and reduction of abuse or misuse of monitored drugs. A systematic review of prescription pattern monitoring studies and their effectiveness in promoting rational use of medicines need to be carried out.

METHODOLOGY:

Aim of the study is to monitor and assess the prescribing patterns of antibiotics.

Study design

It is a prospective and observational study using in patient prescriptions from General medicine department.

Study duration:

Six months from August -January from general medicine department of RIMS, Kadapa.

Study population:

A total of 300 were taken.

Inclusion criteria:

The study includes if the subject satisfies all of the following criteria

- Patient admitted in the department of inpatient General medicine.
- Patients prescribed for any of the antibiotics.
- Patients of either sex were included in the study.

Exclusion criteria:

- Patient who are non-cooperative and who are not prescribed with at least one antibiotics were excluded from the study.
- Pregnancy and lactating women were excluded.
- Patients who are consuming other than allopathy medications were excluded.

Source of data

The data will be collected from Inpatients department in RIMS government hospital, Kadapa.

- Demographics characteristics of the patient from the case sheets.
- Data would be collected from case notes and personnel interview of the subjects who are included in the study at General medicine I.P department.

Method of collection of data:

It is a prospective, observational study to be conducted in RIMS hospital in the department of General medicine.

Data collection would be done by using the following documents.

- Annexure-1a.(Patient Data Collection Form)
- Annexure-1b.(WHO prescribing indicators)

Statistical analysis

- Microsoft excel is used for recording and analysing the data of recruited subjects, and the results were applied in percentage.

RESULTS:

Gender Distribution:

Total 300 prescriptions were collected during study period from general medicine ward of RIMS. Out of sample size, 162 patients were male and 138 were female. The percentage of male and female were 54.0% and 46.0% respectively.

Age distribution:

Out of 300 patients included in the study from inpatient general medicine department, 81 (27%) patients had an age of 13-30 years, 84(28%) patients had an age of 31-45years, 70 (23.3%) patients had an

age of 46-60years, and 65 (21.7%) patients had an age of 61 and above 60 years.

Prescribing pattern of different class of antibiotics:

Out of 300 antibiotics prescribed in the study, 192 (33.9%) Cephalosporins antibiotics were most frequently prescribed antibiotics followed by 125(22.1%) were of Penicillin's, 101(17.8%) were of Macrolides, 56(9.9%) were of Tetracycline's, 50(8.89%) were of Fluoroquinolones, 26(4.63%) were of Antiprotozoals, 13(2.3%) were of Aminoglycosides antibiotics, and 2(0.3%) were of

Figure 1: Prescribing pattern of different class of antibiotics

Disease diagnosed:

Out of 300 patients included in the study from inpatient general medicine department, most common prevalence of disease among study population was COPD 59 (19.6%) followed by Pneumonia 45 (14.9%), Others 44 (14.6%), LRTI 42 (13.9%), Malaria 30 (9.9%), Dengue 25 (8.3%), UTI 19 (6.3%), Fever 12 (4.00%), Asthma 10 (3.3%), Acute GE 7 (2.3%), Combination 4 (1.3%), and Seizures 03(0.9%).

Figure 2: list of Disease diagnosed

Diagnosis pattern in different age group:

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is most common disease observed in our study in 61 Years and above 30 (46.15%). Pneumonia is 31-45 Years 22 (25.28%) and 46-60 years 17(25.37%), and remaining disease seen in below figure 3.

Figure 3: Diagnosis pattern in different age group

Frequency of individual antibiotic for specific diagnosis:

Ceftriaxone was most commonly prescribed antibiotics in Dengue, Malaria, Seizure, Acute GE, Asthma, and others disease. Azithromycin is most commonly prescribed antibiotics for LRTI, Pneumonia, and Asthma. Doxycycline is most commonly prescribed antibiotics for Malaria, Dengue and LRTI.

Figure 4: Frequency of individual antibiotic for specific diagnosis

Based on dosage forms:

In the present study we observed that the most of the drugs prescribed in the forms of injection (64%) followed by tablets (38%) and capsule (2.1%).

Based on number of antibiotics prescribed per patient:

The number of drugs received by patients in the present study out of 300 prescriptions included for the study, 124 (42%) prescriptions had two antimicrobial drugs, 112 (37%) prescriptions had antimicrobial monotherapy, 64 (21%) prescriptions were three or more than three antimicrobial drugs was observed.

Figure 5: number of antibiotics prescribed per patient

Prescribing indicators:

Average number of drugs per encounter was 7.2. Antibiotics were (100%) per encounter. Most of drugs were prescribed from EDL of hospital. Most of the drugs prescribed were injectables. The majority (92.2%) of the drugs were prescribed in generic name.

DISCUSSION:

Prescription monitoring studies are important for obtaining data about the patterns and quality of use, the determinants of drug use, and the outcomes of use. The WHO drug use indicators are highly standardized and are recommended for inclusion in drug utilization studies.

In this study, antimicrobial prescribing pattern was analysed in 300 prescriptions. There were more male patient as compared to females. In our study most of the population were from 31-45 age groups. The most common prevalent disease among study population was COPD 59(19.6%) followed by Pneumonia. Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is most common disease observed in 61 years and above 45 years. Pneumonia is most common disease observed in 31-45 years age group and 22 and 46-60 years.

In the present study we observed that Cephalosporins group of antibiotics are most commonly prescribed

followed by Penicillin's, Macrolides, Tetracycline's, Fluroquinolones, Antiprotozoals, Amino glycosides antibiotics and sulphonamides. Ceftriaxone was most commonly prescribed antibiotic in Dengue, Malaria, Seizure, Acute GE, Asthma and other disease. The study is similar to the Muhammad Atif et al., study. Azithromycin is most commonly prescribed antibiotic for the treatment of LRTI, Pneumonia, Ciprofloxacin is one of the frequently prescribed Quinolone antibiotics for the treatment of UTI, deserves continued monitoring. In our study we observed that antibiotic Dual therapy is commonly prescribed followed by antibiotic monotherapy.

This study states that average number of drugs per encounter was 7.2. Antibiotics were prescribed with 100% per encounter and most of drugs were prescribed from EDL of hospital which is similar to the study of Suparna Sharma et al. The excessive use of Parentrals is common in many developing countries. In this study most of antibiotics were given by Parenteral dosage form, which is more, and it is similar to the study of P.Sneha Pallavi, B. Teja Sree and P.V et al. Study (2016). The majority of the drugs were prescribed in generic name.

CONCLUSION:

In our study we observed COPD disease most common disease. Cephalosporins were most

commonly prescribed class of antibiotics. Among them ceftriaxone was most prescribed antibiotics. Generic prescribing was comparatively higher and mainly prescribed from Essential Drug List. The parenteral use of antibiotics administration was markedly higher. Strict adherence to the prescription policy can significantly overcome the overuse of antibiotics and reduce the development of resistance to antibiotics.

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AUTHORS CONTRIBUTIONS:

All the authors equally contributed to drafting the paper. All authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS:

All authors have none to declare

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